

Publication Date: 04.02.2024

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Promotional activities in the enterprise

Abstract

If we observe and analyze the important changes in the concept of business management between several countries of the world, we can conclude that there are two concepts of business management, and they are:

- according to the first concept, when it is desired to increase production, all the factors that enter into production are studied, and
- the second, in addition to the study of these factors, market research and forecasts are also included.

Due to mass production, contemporary productions are faced with the problem of sales, because the supply is greater than the demand. The amount of products that cannot be sold is a problem. How to sell these products and release funds in so that they can be included in the reproduction process again, these are questions that must be chosen by the leading structures.

To solve these problems, a new philosophy was born, called marketing. This is the system by which successful companies manage to overcome the sales problem. The marketing approach has changed the attitudes and behaviors of companies, orienting them towards the market and consumers. Under the action of these orientations, companies start from the interests and needs of consumers and adapt their products and business according to them. Such an approach allows you to progress relatively quickly, differentiating yourself from those who have not understood the essence and importance of marketing.

Marketing is a new strategic philosophy which has changed the behavior and appearance of enterprises in their business goals. The change lies in the fact that under the action of marketing, the company has the consumer at the center of all its goals, then plans, strategy and actions, and not only its interests - profit. The needs, demands and wishes of customers are the starting point and orientation for production and business of the enterprise.

Keywords: Factoring, industry, world, Kosovo.

The object of the research

The dynamics of the development of the commercial economy also affect the changes and transformations of the traditional approach to the theory and practice of marketing.

Marketing in the past has mainly focused on "the most sales". Whereas today marketing focuses on the consumer in building relationships with all interested parties, especially with consumers.

Therefore, the purpose of the company's marketing activities, in addition to the development of production/service, providing a relevant environment, internal and external communication, is also the fulfillment of the needs and wishes of consumers in a way that ensures the increase in the sale of products/services and ensuring profit in the long term.

Contemporary business requires the development of a good product, to form an adequate price and to make it accessible to consumers. Then, businesses also need to communicate with their intermediaries, consumers and the public.

Promotion is a mechanism of communication, exchange of information between the producer and the consumer. His task is to inform, to remind and convince the customer to react to the organization's products. The reaction can be a purchase, a change of mind or some physical work, eg going to the store.

Promotion represents the only instrument of communicative character in combination with marketing instruments and in the complete commercial affirmation of other elements of the marketing offer. It is necessary to communicate the needs efficiently, to solve the customer's problem in the selection process during the purchase.

Research methodology

The methodology used is extremely important in scientific research, because it is the main guarantee that scientific methods have been used for the research object.

In this work on the general theory and analysis of the research results, with special emphasis is the development of the theoretical structure in combination with the practical one.

Taking into account the specificity of the research object, various methods have been used in order to meet the basic requirements of the research, such as objectivity, security, generality and systematization, then scientific-theoretical knowledge, relevant literature and contemporary work practice have been researched.

THE MARKETING MIX

The marketing mix represents the combination of controlled marketing instruments that the company uses to achieve the appropriate level of sales. The marketing mix represents the mix of all marketing functions in the compilation of the company's marketing plan. In the literature, the most frequent classification of marketing mix elements, or marketing mix functions, is based on the 4Ps, such as:

1. The product
2. Price

3. Promotion and

4. Country.

Most companies or businesses will change the marketing mix used from case to case or from market to market depending on differences in national culture, economic development, standards of the tourist product offered, distribution channels used, etc.

The optimal marketing mix includes the creative adaptation of additional activities or elements, so that the product or service is offered to the market under the most favorable conditions, in order to achieve the company's goals. Marketing instruments are used for strategic marketing purposes. First of all, to have the right production at the right price, in the right place, with the right promotion, in order to achieve the best possible results against the competition. All elements of the marketing mix must be good and in accordance with the needs and demands of consumers.

Production (product) as an instrument of the marketing mix

The product ie. that the product or service that the company offers in the target market.

The production is created as a result of the efforts of all employees in the company to adapt to the needs and demands of the market. The needs of buyers-consumers do not exist because of certain products, but to be fulfilled in the use of products.

The production/product is a very dynamic instrument of the marketing mix. The possibilities for refinement, modification and change of the product are great. Production is the materialized result of human labor, which is offered to the market in order to satisfy the needs or desires of consumers. It is important that the production and creation of products should be started from the needs and demands of consumers.

The product mix (assortment) represents the collection of all product lines and items that a given supplier offers to buyers in the market. Product mix is reflected in terms of width, depth, line length and consistency.

The basic distinguishing marks of the product are related to design, quality, production functionality, brand, packaging and labeling as well as production-related services.

Even the protective mark is as important as the name, which serves to protect the producer and the consumer from possible counterfeiting and to distinguish the products from similar or the same ones and to guarantee the quality of production.

The design must first of all contribute to the connectivity and determination of the qualitative properties for the construction of the product, in order to attract consumers. By industrial design we mean the activities, the purpose of which is the creative application of scientific knowledge from the side of art, the application of painting, as well as all the knowledge from the side of engineering, as well as the ability to form the product, the concept and the definition of the product.

In a broad sense, design represents the visual, functional and qualitative formation of all living conditions of the community/community. The fundamental purpose of design is to connect consumer desire with the product. He must ensure the harmony of color, appearance, style and functionality of the product. A good designer must know the functionality of the product, have knowledge in marketing, in the appearance of the product, as well as the wishes, needs and habits of consumers. Quality can be defined as the comprehensive and characteristic existence of the product/service based on their ability to meet the needs of consumers. The term quality itself unifies many product qualities or features, such

as durability, precision, reliability, safe and easy use, functionality and user value.

The brand serves to distinguish a product from other or similar products in the market. but also as information about the origin and source of the product. The product-brand is the name of the term, sign, symbol or their combination, which aims to identify the goods or services of a producer or group of producers and differentiate them from competing goods. So, by brand we understand the term, sign, symbol, drawing or any combination of these elements that serve to identify the products and services of a seller or group of sellers that differentiates them from competitors.

Defining the company's mission

Every business organization exists for a mission of its own. At the beginning of its existence, every company has a clearly defined mission, but during the business period it becomes unclear mainly for the reasons of the attachment of new products and the markets in which it does business. . In this direction, these questions help, which give clear direction of the behavior of the business organizational team, such as:

- what is our job?
- who is our buyer-end consumer?
- what do buyers value in our company?
- where is our business going?
- what should our business look like etc....?

These seemingly simple questions are among the most difficult for the company to answer. The mission reflects the purpose of the company's existence - what the company wants to achieve in the business environment, and a well-chosen one that serves as an "invisible hand" that guides the employees in the company, in the sense that regardless of the teams, work and accomplish the tasks their organizational.

When forming the mission, managers should have three key elements in mind:

- the history of the organization,
- its distinctive advantages and
- the environment in which it operates. 27

It is also necessary to define the production mission from the business one, because very often companies declare themselves depending on what they do, what they get, e.g. "we produce furniture".

CASE RESEARCH

PURPOSE

The main purpose of this research has to do with collecting the most complete information on the financial situation of Kosovar families, their satisfaction with the businesses where they are supplied, in other words, what is the weight of the Kosovar basket.

Reason

This survey presents the results of the survey of 70 consumers who made purchases at the "VIVA-FRESH" company in Gjilan, conducted in the period from 12.06.2014 to 17.06.2014, where the interviews lasted an average of 10-15 minutes. The surveys were conducted through face-to-face (face-to-face) interviews with the consumer.

The age of 19-30 years is the most targeted during the interview, for the reason that this age consumes the most products/services that the company "Viva-fresh" offers.

SAMPLE

The research included respondents who were interviewed in the premises of this company. This sample has been considered to be representative and comprehensive in order to better reflect the opinion of consumers. Respondents are adults. The respondents are from both sexes, as men, but also women from different professions, such as: lawyer, economist, technologist, administrative officer, teacher, inspector, translator, police officer, seller, teacher, cashier, laboratory technician, pharmacist, doctor, worker, housewife, photographer, student, nurse, pupil, etc. We consider the number of respondents to be an optimally representative sample that reflects consumers' purchases of their products for a month.

The number of 70 respondents was the planned sample size.

ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

I conducted this interview with passersby-consumers of the case and with random selection. The transparency and honesty in the responses given by the customers is rated as very satisfactory. As a result, the vast majority of respondents prefer this company because it is cheaper than its sister companies, then the service is at the level, so they consume more of the products that the company in question offers.

Other findings during the interview, which are also the determining elements in the purchase of products, are:

- they usually make the purchases themselves,
- expiration date and origin of the products,
- quality of products,
- they usually plan their purchases in advance,
- are little familiar with product standards,
- they usually use large carts for shopping,
- price is a determining element in the purchase of products,
- printing material and promotional offers, etc.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Most companies, regardless of whether they are large, medium, small or micro enterprises, encounter the same problem - high prices. High prices are seen as an obstacle in the realization of the sales plan.

The orientation of all work activities of the "VIVA-FRESH" company is to have the customer at the center of attention. Therefore, in order to realize this commitment, the company needs to be informed about the opinions, perceptions and problems of consumers, as well as the quality of the services it offers. This information serves the company "VIVA-FRESH" as a guide on which it plans and focuses its efforts in addressing the concerns of consumers and consequently improves the specific aspects of services with which consumers are dissatisfied or less satisfied.

Buyers brag about successful purchases, but also vent about the failure of a product or service.

Marketing must take into account the nature of communication with consumers, which is related to the types of communication, then how communication is carried out, the conditions for its realization as well as the motive of individuals, then information about the product, advice about it, opinion or suggestions in connection with the brand, as well as information about the experience.

Conclusion

In order to face the aggressive competition in the market of Kosovo in new circumstances and conditions as well as the position of our state, there is no room for complacency, the new conditions necessarily impose on us the way of acting in the market, and that:

- to continue increasing the quality of services to consumers,
- to organize more frequent sensitization campaigns with consumers,
- increasing the efficiency of complaints (if any) and customer requests,
- assortment and high quality of products,
- advertising of services and products,
- purchase and distribution of advertising material,
- constant competition in the market with competitive prices, etc.

These are some elements that must be done in order for customers to be satisfied with our services, therefore the success of the company is guaranteed.

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